

A MODEL STUDY OF INTERPHASE FORMATION IN SILANISED EPOXY RESIN USING NANOINDENTATION

S Behzadi, SA Hayes, FR Jones

Department of Engineering Materials, University of Sheffield, Sir Robert Hadfield Building, Mappin Street, Sheffield, S1 3JD, UK

ABSTRACT: An interphase between silanised and non-silanised epoxy resins was simulated by sandwiching the two castings together and post-curing. In this way a comprehensible interface was maintained while allowing some silane migration to occur at the boundary. The two epoxy resins were extensively characterised by DMTA analysis. The effect of silane additions to the resin was studied in detail. Both as-received and hydrolysed γ -APS silane were used in the study. The mechanical properties were determined using nanoindentation with a Berkovich indenter attached to a Hysitron/DI AFM which also allows the interface to be imaged. It was demonstrated that an interphase region existed between the two epoxy resins in the absence of the silane. On addition of the silane to one component, the interphase thickness increased at a rate of 10% per wt.% silane addition.

KEY TERMS: Epoxy resin, silane coupling agent, hydrolysed silane, model interphase, DMTA, AFM, Nanoindentation, Interphase thickness.

INTRODUCTION

In the fabrication of a polymer composite the sizing on the glass fibre, which contains a polymeric film former (often epoxy resin) and a silane coupling agent, forms an interphase region at the fibre surface. The silane oligomers present can diffuse while the polymeric component will stay bonded to the glass fibre to act as a coupling agent. The interphase can be considered, therefore, to be a semi interpenetrating network. In this paper, we have simulated this process by preparing a "silanised epoxy resin" which has been bonded to non-silanised resin of differing mechanical properties. Thus the mechanical properties across this model interphase have been studied by nanoindentation.

EXPERIMENTAL

The resin (as sizing or as matrix) used in this study was the mixture of Epikote 828 (Shell), a diglycidyl ether of Bisphenol A (DGEBA) epoxy resin and Araldite GY298 (Ciba-Geigy), a long chain aliphatic epoxy resin. The resins were cured with Nadic Methyl Anhydride (NMA) (Stag Polymers and Sealants), and Capcure 3-800 (Henkel Performance Chemicals), a mercaptan terminated curing agent. The resin systems were distinguished by the ratio of Epikote 828 to GY298. Stoichiometric quantities of the two curing agents were added as shown in Table 1. The resin was degassed at 80°C for 10 minutes and cast into silicone rubber moulds where it was cured for 4 hours at 80°C followed by post-curing for 3 hours at 130°C.

The epoxy resin 80-20 was blended with a hydrolysed silane coupling agent γ -Aminopropyltriethoxysilane (γ -APS A1100) to simulate the size applied to glass fibre. A solute of silane in methanol at a ratio of 1:9 was hydrolysed in a 0.2 M solution of acetic acid in distilled water. It is known that the resultant solution contains a high proportion of the silane triols, which are relatively stable [1]. The solution was then concentrated by rotary evaporation under vacuum at 60°C. The soluble components, which are silane triols and siloxane oligomers have higher boiling points than the solvent so that a residue of soluble hydrolysed silane was prepared. 1-5 wt.% mixtures of both the as-received and hydrolysed γ -APS was blended with the epoxy resin 80-20 blend was prepared.

Resin system		
Components	20-80	80-20
Epikote 828	20	80
Araldite GY298	80	20
NMA	45.98	72.87
Capcure 3-800	17.20	27.26

Table.1. Composition of blended epoxy resin by weight.

Dynamic Mechanical Thermal Analysis (DMTA)

The tests were carried out on samples of dimension 30x10x2 mm³ using a DMTA Mk III (Rheometric Scientific Ltd, Epsom, Surrey) such that the sample was subjected to a 1% strain, 1 Hz forced oscillation frequency and 2 K/min heating rate over the temperature range of 30°C to 130°C.

Nanoindentation

All indentation tests were performed using the Hysitron Triboscope attached to a *DI Dimension*TM 3100 AFM. In this equipment a dedicated nanoindentation transducer and scanner is attached in place of the AFM scanner and tip assembly. This allows samples to be imaged with the indenter tip, in a manner analogous to contact mode AFM, prior to selection of a location for measurement by indentation. The resolution of the loading and the displacement systems was 100 nN and 0.1 nm, respectively. The probe was a Berkovich (pyramidal) diamond tip with a radius of approximately 100 nm, whose geometry and indent profile are shown in Fig. 1. The 10x10x2 mm³ cured samples were glued onto a small disk-shaped metal section to minimise any creep in the sample under the load. Accurate calibration against a standard fused silica sample with relatively low elastic modulus ($E= 72$ GPa), high hardness ($H= 9$ GPa) [2] and large elastic recovery during unloading, enables fully quantitative determination of its mechanical properties as shown in Fig.2. Thermal drift calibration was adjusted to account for small amounts of thermal expansion or contraction in the material or the indenter during the test and performed for each individual indentation over 20 seconds. Tip-area function calibration was determined from a series of indentations at different loads on the standard sample, giving a wide range of depths. The tip area function is of the form

$$A = C_2d^2 + C_2d + C_3d^{1/2} + C_4d^{1/4} + C_5d^{1/8} \quad (1)$$

where $C_1 - C_5$ are constants and d is the depth.

Indentation cycle consisted of loading to the maximum in 5 s which was held for a further 5 s before unloading over 5 s. To check the reproducibility of the data, a range of indentations were carried out at increasing intervals of 200 μ N. To avoid interference from plastic deformation, the indents were separated by 20 – 30 times the maximum depth.

Fig.1.(a) Geometry of Berkovich indenter tip[3], (b) Plastic deformation by Berkovich indentation on an Aluminium substrate [2].

Fig.2. Typical indentation load-displacement curve of fused quartz as a standard sample performed at load of 1000 μN.

Preparation of a Model Interphase between Epoxy Resins

The 80-20 epoxy resin containing 0-5 wt.% hydrolysed silane (HAPS) and the 20-80 epoxy resin were pregelled for 200 and 260 minutes respectively, at 80°C and then laminated. The latent polymerisation of the gelled resins allows interdiffusion of the components. The approach was chosen so that a physically distinct interface was present between the resins of differing properties. In this way we could ensure that we were analysing the correct region.

The simulated interphase between these two epoxy resins was studied by nanoindentation to provide profiles of mechanical properties within this region. To ensure a smooth surface for study, the samples were fractured between notches at liquid nitrogen temperature. Starting with the 20-80 resin, indents were placed horizontally at 3 μm intervals across the interface and interphase onto the 80-20 resin. This could be automated using the Triboscope® 4.0 AT. The applied load was kept constant at 500 N.

RESULTS

Characterisation of the Silane/Epoxy Resin Blend

Dynamic Mechanical Thermal Analysis (DMTA) was used to monitor the glass transition temperature (T_g) of the epoxy resin 80-20/silane (γ -APS or HAPS) blends. For each epoxy resin/ γ -APS blend system, three samples were selected and tested individually by DMTA and the average properties were recorded. γ -APS/epoxy resin 80-20 blend proved to be unsuitable for the nanoindentation test because of problems with degassing and the more appropriate HAPS/epoxy blend was used. Fig. 3 shows the effect of γ -APS and HAPS on the T_g of the 80-20 epoxy resin.

Fig.3. Comparison of two different silanes influence on T_g response of Epoxy resin 80-20.

The unhydrolysed γ -APS caused a more rapid reduction in T_g than the prehydrolysed silane (HAPS). What is interesting is that in Fig. 4 it is seen that the storage modulus above T_g in the rubbery region remains approximately constant up to 4% addition of HAPS while the unhydrolysed silane had a significant effect. This shows that the average degrees of crosslinking in the HAPS modified resin are similar. Taken together with the reduction in T_g this can be interpreted as the formation of a semi-interpenetrating network in this case.

Fig.4. E_r (Rubbery storage modulus) changes due to addition of γ -APS and HAPS to Epoxy resin 80-20 system.

Nanoindentation Testing of the Interphase Region Between the Epoxy Resins

To examine the change in modulus across the interface between the two epoxy resins of differing mechanical properties, the indentations have been performed at the same load of 500 μN . Three regions with differing properties were observed. There was clearly an interphase between the soft 20-80 resin and the stiffer 80-20 resin. Fig.5. shows that the interphase was $\approx 15 \mu\text{m}$ either side of the interface.

Fig.5. The positioning of the interphase region on the Reduced modulus and Hardness profiles for 20-80/80-20 Control system at the load of 500 μN .

Simulated Interphase Between Epoxy Resin 20-80 and Silanised Epoxy Resin 80-20

Since the nanoindentation technique requires a very smooth surface for automated examination of the interphase region, samples were fractured at liquid nitrogen temperatures. The fracture surfaces were profiled using the nanoindenter probe in AFM mode to identify the interphase region.

(a) AFM 3D contrast image of Control 80-20/20-80

(b) AFM 3D contrast image of 2 wt.% HAPS 80-20/20-80.

Fig.6. 3D AFM images of interface between (a) 80-20/20-80 epoxy resin sandwich, (b) HAPS (2% silanised) Epoxy resin 80-20/20-80 sandwich.

The transition or interphase region can arise from the interdiffusion of HAPS from the silanised resin into the epoxy resin 20-80. The effect of variations in silane concentration on the thickness of the transition zone was studied. As shown in Table 2 the interphase thickness is strongly dependent on silane coupling agent concentrations.

HAPS Conc. (Wt.%) in Epoxy Resin 80-20	Thickness from E_r Profile (μm)	Thickness from Hardness Profile (μm)
0	27.94	25.27
1	30.90	27.80
3	36.98	35.34
4	39.53	38.50

Table 2. Thickness of the simulated interphase for the different HAPS/Epoxy resin 80-20 systems, estimated from the Hardness and Modulus profile.

An alternative explanation for these observations may arise from the location of the indent on the interface causing non homogenous deformation as shown in Fig.7. To check this, indents were made at the lower loads of 100 and 300 μN to examine this boundary effect.

Table 3 shows that the interphase between the two resins in the absence of the silane, is still present at the same dimensions. Reducing the load should have had a major effect if it was an artefact of the load geometry.

Fig.7. Schematic representation of boundary effects in the sandwiched samples.

Indentation load (μN)	Interphase Thickness from Er Profile (μm)	Interphase Thickness from Hardness Profile (μm)
100	27.52	24.22
300	27.40	24.45
500	27.94	25.27

Table 3. The influence of indentation load on the interphase thickness across 80-20/20-80 resin interface.

DISCUSSION

The presence of a size on glass fibres can lead to the formation of a three-dimensional interphase region around the fibre, which can have a profound effect on the micromechanics of glass reinforced fibre composites.

The objective of this work was to simulate the formation of an interphase region through silane diffusion, in the absence of the constraining glass substrate, which can lead to reports of unusually high interphase moduli [4,5,6].

The unhydrolysed silane γ -APS was found to lead to a significant decrease in the glass transition temperature (T_g) of the resin, as shown in Fig.3. Furthermore, because hydrolysis occurred within the resin degassing proved difficult with the result that the samples for nanoindentation were not satisfactory. However, in practice, the silane is added to an aqueous based emulsified resin for coating the glass fibres and therefore will be in the form of hydrolysed oligomers. Some polymerisation will occur at the fibre surface on drying the fibres. A close representation therefore is to prehydrolyse the silane and redissolve it into the epoxy resin to simulate the coating on the glass fibre.

Prehydrolysis of γ -APS was used to give a soluble HAPS. This could be dissolved in the epoxy resin 80-20 and caused a reduction in T_g (Fig. 3). However, the modulus of the resin (above T_g) was not affected, in contrast to the unhydrolysed γ -APS. The conclusion is that the average crosslink density of the cured resin remained the same so that a semi-interpenetrating network must have formed.

Therefore the formation of an interphase region between two epoxy resins can occur through diffusion of the HAPS oligomers, in the adjacent epoxy resin (20-80 in this experiment).

By fitting lines to the three regions in the Hardness and Reduced Modulus profiles, in Fig.5, the thickness of the interphase region could be estimated. Fig.8 gives the results of this analysis. The interphase region is shown to increase linearly with the silane concentration in the 80-20 resin. This can be understood to be a result of the higher rate of migration of HAPS oligomers into the gelled 20-80 resin at higher concentrations of silane. This leads to diffusion over a larger length scale.

Fig.8. Variation of simulated interphase thickness in HAPS/Epoxy resin systems.

CONCLUSIONS

Depending on its concentration, the Epoxy resin compatible γ -APS silane coupling agent (A1100), causes a reduction in the thermomechanical properties of the sizing resin. This probably is caused by the migration of the oligomeric silane components into the surrounding sizing resin and by penetration of the resin into the polymeric component.

The Hydrolysed γ -APS silane (HAPS) did not have a major influence on the mechanical properties of the epoxy resin 80-20 at room temperature, which was interpreted to mean that a semi-interpenetrating structure formed. On addition of HAPS the thickness of the simulated interphase increased linearly with concentration. It is concluded that the interphase only formed by interdiffusion of the silane from the resin to the other during cure, since there was no evidence of a tip geometry effect.

REFERENCES

- 1.Plueddemann, E.P., Silane Coupling Agents, 2nd ed, 1991, New York: Plenum press
2. Hay, J.C. and G.M. Pharr, Instrumented Indentation Testing, MTS System Corporation.
- 3.Hodzic, A., Z.H. Stachurski and J.K. Kim, Nano-indentation of Polymer/Glass Interfaces: Part I. Experimental and Mechanical Analysis, Polymer, 2000, **41**, 6895-6905.
- 4.Hodzic, A., et al., Application of Nano-indentation, Nano-scratch and Single Fibre Tests in Investigation of Interphase in Composite Materials, Micron, 2001, **32**, 765-775.
- 5.Hodzic, A., J.K. Kim and Z.H. Stachurski, Nano-indentation and Nano-scratch of Polymer/Glass Interfaces: II. Model of Interphases in Water Aged Composite Materials. Polymer, 2001, **42**, 5701-5710.
- 6.Gao, S. and E. Mader, Characterisation of Interphase Nanoscale Property in Glass Fibre Reinforced Polypropylene and Epoxy Resin Composites, Composites: Part A, 2002, **33**, 559-576.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We thank EPSRC for a grant to purchase the Nanoindentation instrument.